

SOURCES OF EMERGENCE OF KORAKALPOK'S STORIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7743491>

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Abstract: The article describes the sources and stages of development of Karakalpak narratives. The genre nature of Karakalpak narratives and their place in the system of folk prose are given. The difference of narration from other genres of oral prose is defined. It is said that there is an effect of contaminating, retrospective methods in the emergence of narratives. He defined the difference of narration from other genres of oral prose and the commonalities between them.

Keywords: folklore, narrative, genre feature, folk prose.

Received: 16-03-2023

Accepted: 17-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

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SOURCES AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF KORAKALPOK STORIES

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Abstract: В статье описаны источники и этапы развития каракалпакских нарративов. Дана жанровая природа каракалпакских сказок и их место в системе народной прозы. Определяется отличие повествования от других жанров устной прозы. Говорят, что в появлении нарративов есть эффект загрязняющих, ретроспективных методов. Он определил отличие повествования от других жанров устной прозы и общие черты между ними..

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Creation of the classification of folk prose works, comprehensive study of historical-genetic foundations, genre composition and artistry of oral prose has become one of the priority scientific directions in contemporary world folklore studies. Catalogs of epic plots and motifs created as a result of improvement of the historical-geographical method developed by the Finnish school of folklore by English, German, Hungarian, Turkish and Russian scholars, oral prose works, including extensive research on genre specificity, national characteristics and typology of narratives. was the basis for the increase.

The theoretical concepts and research methods of world folklore studies on the genesis, classification, and poetics of folk prose have started a new stage of collecting, systematizing, preparing for publication, and studying materials related

to epic genres of Karakalpak folklore, such as fairy tales, legends, narratives, and narratives.

Determining the genre nature of narratives, their place in the system of folk prose, the uniqueness of the plot series and the composition of motives will be the basis for further enriching the theory of Karakalpak folklore. After all, the study of the genre features, poetic features and sources of the plot system of Karakalpak narratives allows to determine the stages of development and artistic evolution of folklore.

Karakalpak folk tales are distinguished from other genres of folklore by reflecting the historical reality and customs of the past on the basis of life fiction. The life path of our people is expressed in the narratives, which are revered as masterpieces of intangible cultural heritage, "this priceless wealth will undoubtedly serve as a source of wisdom and knowledge for new and new generations, and most importantly, a solid ground for new discoveries" [1, 2017 Decision No. PQ-3080 of June 23]

The narrative genre in Karakalpak folk prose was not the object of research on a separate monographic basis. That is why it is natural to encounter some difficulties during his studies. Because of this, taking into account the many problems of the genre that need to be researched, we decided to scientifically analyze the most important of them in our work. When reacting to a specific folklore work, the first priority is to determine its genre characteristics. Because there is no logic in thinking about the work without studying its specific nature. This issue becomes particularly important when it comes to narration. The goal can be achieved by defining the difference between narrative and other genres of oral prose and the commonalities between them. When studying a certain genre in world literature, its national characteristics are taken into account. That is why it is illogical to talk about the existence of common, unchanging themes for all national narratives. In the article, special attention was paid to the national symbols of the genre when determining the scope of the narratives.

Sources of emergence of Karakalpak folk narratives Our scientific observations on the issue of the emergence of narratives have been expressed. Among the samples of Karakalpak folk oral poetic creation, the sources of the narrative genre have a multi-level character. It is distinguished from other genres by the fact that real historical events, historical figures, nations, peoples and peoples appear, are named, and are created depending on certain geographical places. Evidence of a historical nature serves as a basis for the emergence of each narrative. Narration is oral history, history in the minds of the people. Narratives serve to interpret real events [2, 176] sources of origin of narratives to determine the stages and principles

of their development. So, the main source of narratives is history, life reality, geographical location, real historical person and creative attitude to them.

Contaminating, retrospective methods also have a certain effect on the emergence of narratives. The cases of mixing of different events around one historical narrative object or the interaction of a relatively later historical event with pre-existing legendary concepts make the narrative more comprehensive and enrich it. The creator of the narrative has an artistic-aesthetic attitude to reality and strives to completely idealize it. Subsequent performers also add their creative "shares" to the work.

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As the ways of the creation of narratives are always connected with historical periods, the stages of its creation also acquire multi-layeredness. That is, when studying the sources of narrations, attention should be paid to their periodic descriptions, socio-historical characteristics. However, the mechanism of creation of narratives is based on general principles for all periods.

The time when Karakalpak folk tales appeared and the period of their formation and development are determined based on the content of the events described in the works. They are social in nature. Characteristic events in any society can be expressed in narratives. Due to the fact that the relations and traditions of our ancestors had a strong influence on the creation of narratives, their formation was directly related to the social development of society.

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